

Lung-area Restricted CT Generation via Conditional Score-Based Diffusion Models

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Abstract

Chest CT scans are vital for diagnosing lung abnormalities, yet their use in Deep Learning is limited by data scarcity, labeling costs, and privacy concerns. This work explores Score-based Diffusion Models for conditional CT slice generation restricted to the lung area. Two cases are considered: conditioning on lung masks, and on both lung and nodule masks. Custom U-Net architectures are trained under Variance Preserving (VP) and Variance Exploding (VE) stochastic differential equations to compare diffusion trajectories.

VP SDEs achieve higher fidelity, with better FID, MMD, and SSIM than VE. Generated images follow conditioning closely, producing realistic lung and nodule structures for data augmentation. While current success is limited to 2D slices, future work targets 3D generation and richer anatomical conditioning. In essence, these results highlight the promise of conditional diffusion models for computer-aided diagnosis and Deep Learning in lung disease analysis.

1 Introduction

Chest CT scans are vital in diagnosing lung abnormalities, particularly lung cancer, one of the leading causes of cancer-related deaths. While deep learning has advanced computer-aided diagnosis of lung nodules, progress is hindered by limited data availability. Building large annotated datasets requires costly expert labeling and faces additional restrictions from privacy and data protection regulations.

Data augmentation provides a partial solution, but common traditional analytical methods such as rotations or cropping often fail to preserve anatomical correctness in medical images. Generative AI models have therefore emerged as a more powerful alternative, enabling the creation of realistic medical synthetic data for training. Generative Adversarial Networks have long dominated the field despite unstable training and limited scalability [4]. More recently, Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models and Score-based Models have surpassed GANs in image fidelity [3], gaining traction in medical imaging.

This work explores Score-based Diffusion Models [5] for conditional generation of lung CT slices. We evaluate two scenarios: conditioning on lung segmentation masks to constrain anatomical content, and conditioning on both lung and nodule masks to guide the synthesis of nodule-like structures.

2 Methodology

2.1 Score-based Diffusion Models

Score-based diffusion models generate images by simulating a forward and reverse diffusion process, where noise is gradually added to the data and then progressively removed to reconstruct realistic samples [5].

To generate new images, the process is reversed using a Stochastic Differential Equation (SDE), relying on the score function, $\nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \log p_t(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{y})$, i.e. the gradient of the data distribution at different noise levels given a conditional mapping. The score is then estimated by a trained time-informed conditional neural network. By solving the reverse-time SDE

in Equation 1, it is possible to produce samples with the trained score-prediction model.

$$d\mathbf{x} = [\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, t) - g(t)^2 \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \log p_t(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{y})] dt + g(t) d\bar{\mathbf{w}} \quad (1)$$

Two types of SDEs are explored: Variance Preserving (VP) and Variance Exploding (VE). The VP SDE maintains a controlled noise level throughout the diffusion process, while the VE SDE introduces larger noise scales that grow over time [5].

2.2 Dataset and Preprocessing

The dataset for this study was derived from the publicly available Lung Image Database Consortium (LIDC) dataset [1]. The 50% consensus of each nodule annotation set forms the nodule segmentation maps. Furthermore, the lung segmentation masks were generated with the model from [6]. In this work, 80% of the scans were allocated for training and the remaining 20% for testing, ensuring no overlap of CT slices between the two sets. Using the lung and nodule segmentation masks, the content mappings for each slice were labeled as performed in [2], where regions outside the lungs were labeled as 0, lung regions as 1, and nodules as 2.

To address the goal of generating lung content from specific area mappings, two conditional generation tasks were defined. The first relies solely on lung segmentation masks, resulting in a dataset of about 50,000 lung mappings with corresponding CT slices. The second incorporates both lung and nodule masks, yielding a smaller dataset of roughly 4,000 mappings and slices. Since the focus is restricted to synthesizing content within the lungs, all slices were masked to exclude non-lung regions. Finally, min-max normalization was applied, scaling each slice to the [0, 1] range, as part of preprocessing.

Fig. 1 illustrates an example of a data point of the second task dataset: a lung CT scan slice, restricted to the lung region, and its corresponding lung area and nodule area mapping.

2.3 Experimental Setup

The model used in this study follows a typical time-informed U-Net architecture, with skip connections and a shallow Multi-Layer Perceptron

Figure 1: Lung-area restricted CT scan slice (left) and corresponding content mapping (right).

Generative Task	SDE	FID ↓	MMD ↓	SSIM ↑
Lung-only	VP	<u>214.3</u>	<u>0.0135</u>	<u>0.894</u>
	VE	314.0	0.0152	0.788
Lung and Nodule	VP	<u>173.4</u>	<u>0.0133</u>	<u>0.891</u>
	VE	246.1	0.0137	0.768

Table 1: Evaluation metrics values for the models developed for each generative task.

Figure 2: Three examples of samples generated with only lung area conditioning (one per row).

(MLP) to produce time step embeddings. The encoder progressively reduces spatial resolution, while the decoder restores it, with features from each encoder stage concatenated to the corresponding decoder stage. Normalization and residual connections are applied throughout the network to stabilize training. The input consists of a noised, lung-restricted CT image $\mathbf{x}(t)$ channel-concatenated with the conditional mapping \mathbf{y} that guides the generation process.

The training procedure is carried out in two sequential stages, such as in [2]. In the first one, the models are trained solely on data without nodule conditional mappings. This allows them to initially focus on synthesizing realistic lung structures constrained to the lung regions specified in the conditional masks. In the second stage, the models obtained from the previous training are used as pre-trained bases and are further fine-tuned on data that includes nodule conditional mappings. This additional step enables the models to learn how to generate nodule-like content accurately within the designated regions.

In this study, the testing setup is performed with 100 samples of each model, and the following generative evaluation metrics are averaged over 5 test rounds: Fréchet Inception Distance (FID), Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD), and Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM).

3 Results and Discussion

Firstly, regarding lung-only conditional generation, the results show that the VP SDE model consistently outperforms the VE SDE model, achieving higher SSIM and lower distributional distances, given the notably better FID and MMD values, as seen in Table 1. These findings indicate that the VP model not only generates lung structures with greater structural fidelity but also aligns more closely with the overall distribution of real data. Figure 2 displays some samples from both models.

Next, the results for lung and nodule conditional generation show that the VP model outperforms the VE SDE in lung and nodule conditional generation, producing more realistic nodule-like structures and achieving higher structural similarity. Specifically, as framed in Table 1, the VP model attained lower FID and MMD values, indicating better alignment with the real data distribution, as well as a higher SSIM, reflecting improved local and perceptual image quality. Figure 3 shows some samples from both models.

Figure 3: Three examples of samples generated with lung area and nodule area conditioning (one per row).

4 Conclusion

This study successfully implemented score-based diffusion models to generate high-fidelity lung CT scan slices with conditional area mapping, demonstrating that VP SDE models outperformed VE SDE models across all metrics while producing realistic anatomical structures and nodule content. The models effectively followed conditional guidance to synthesize realistic lung shapes and nodule structures, showing promise for data augmentation in deep learning applications. Future research should focus on extending to 3D volumetric synthesis, incorporating comprehensive anatomical variations, quantifying systematic biases, and validating whether synthetic images can meaningfully improve diagnostic model performance, as this approach holds significant potential for advancing medical image generation and computer-aided diagnosis systems.

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